

Representing big mobile data using automated grid systems – an assessment of the quadtree method

Louise Sieg^{*}, James Cheshire[†]

Department of Geography, University College London

January 2021

Summary

This paper explores new methods of anonymising and representing large human-generated datasets (here mobile phone activity data). We use a quadtree algorithm developed by Lagonigro et. al (2020) to spatially aggregate mobile in-app events and compare outputs obtained between days and against an Ordnance Survey grid. We aim to demonstrate potential usage of new computational tools and exemplify their potential to inform more elaborate and project-specific regionalisation methods.

KEYWORDS: Geospatial ‘Big Data’, Urban Analytics, Quadtrees, Regionalisation

Introduction

Aggregating sensitive datasets is central to data protection and the prevention of data-misuse, as de-identification is insufficient to fully protect privacy (de Montjoye et. al, 2018). However, spatial aggregation requires a range of choices to be made concerning the scale at which to aggregate, and the spatial units used. The impacts of these choices on spatial analysis have been demonstrated as part of the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP) and are shown to skew results significantly (Viegas et. al, 2009; Lovelace et. al, 2014). Thus, lessening the impact of MAUP requires project-specific aggregation choices and justifications. Output Areas are a famous example of successful regionalisation for specific use: the collection and output of census statistics (Cockings et. al, 2011). However, despite other successful attempts in land use and transport planning, there are no specific regions or aggregation methods outlined for big human-generated mobile datasets, different in nature to census statistics (Molloy and Moeckel, 2017).

Lagonigro et. al call out more specifically a “lack of specific methods in R to anonymise spatial data” (Lagonigro et. al, 2020, 1). They lay out a first attempt at meeting this need with their R package AQuadtree which uses quadtree algorithms to spatially aggregate data at a given threshold (Lagonigro et. al, 2020, 2). This proposes an automated and reproducible grid system which uses the data to shape the grid, rather than fitting the data to pre-defined areas.

Research aim

In this paper, we apply the Lagonigro et. al quadtree algorithm to an in-app mobile phone location dataset in London demonstrating its usability (Lagonigro et. al, 2020, 2). We argue this type of automated grid system, though not suitable for geodemographic linkage and analysis, could be of great interest to inform projects using similar data and the decisions-making process behind aggregating and zoning. Though it may not be the final solution to efficiently anonymise big human-generated datasets, it can act as a methodological tool for researchers to better grasp and visualise their datasets, thus better informing their regionalisation choices.

^{*} louise.sieg.16@ucl.ac.uk

[†] james.cheshire@ucl.ac.uk

Data

1.1 Mobile phone location dataset

This data was provided by Huq Industries (<https://huq.io/>). It consists of mobile devices' GPS locations and timestamp stored by mobile applications (apps) when the app is being used. The apps seek user's consent to store this information. The dataset is stored securely in an ISO27001 facility with access restricted to researchers who have undertaken the Consumer Data Research Centre (CDRC) accreditation programme and following a multi-stage application process.

1.2 Geographic areas

We subset our Huq dataset to retrieve points over sample days (a Monday in March 2018 and 2020 and a week of rush hour (8-10am) data). We filter the points geographically by joining them to a shapefile of the Greater London Boundary and keeping only those within. Firstly, we generate quadtrees for Greater London to compare between the two dates, and then map the boroughs of Westminster and Tower Hamlets to exemplify the capacity of the dataset to display activity hotspots at a granular scale.

Methodology - Quadtree algorithm by Lagonigro et. al.

A quadtree is a hierarchical subdivision of a plane. The Lagonigro et. al algorithm starts with a square containing input data (here, our in-app event) and recursively subdivides the cells into quadrants, if the number of points in each quadrant is above the set anonymity threshold. Not meeting this threshold means the cell is not further divided. In certain cases, disaggregation requires the removal of very low point counts, for which the algorithm weights the loss rate (how many points must be suppressed) against the lost granularity of the grid that would result from not suppressing. To minimise the information loss, points that are suppressed are added, and if this group exceed the anonymity threshold, they are aggregated into an initial cell and marked as a residual cell.

The maps presented in this paper are made with a threshold of 10 unique devices – meaning each cell meets the non-disclosure requirement of 10 or more devices. We apply the AQuadtree functions to our dataset subsets and discuss below. More details on the algorithm and its functions are available in the package documentation (Lagonigro et. al, 2020, 2).

Results

Figure 1: Unique devices recorded in London, 26th of March 2018, plotted using quadtree hierarchical method, with a threshold of 10 devices minimum per cell. In black are the residual cells.

Figure 2: Unique devices recorded in London, Monday 30th of March 2020, plotted using quadtree hierarchical method – threshold of 10 devices. This was just following the first Lockdown being implemented.

By creating quadtree maps of London at different dates, we can quickly compare activity levels on a Monday in 2018 with a Monday during the first lockdown of 2020. We see **Figure 2** has much lower, sparser counts, and many areas where the unique device count was insufficient for the algorithm to further divide and generate grids. This quickly paints a picture of the activity levels at both dates, in a format which is easily comparable. Removing the need to choose a specific aggregation scale prevents the researcher from having to make assumption based on previous expectations of the data's behaviour.

The following maps show how the quadtree algorithm performs with our in-app data at more granular scales such as London Boroughs and their activity hotspots.

Figure 3: Unique devices recorded in Westminster over rush hours (8-10am) over the course of a week in September. Plotted using quadtree with a threshold of 10.

Figure 4: Huq Activity aggregated to 250x250 metre grid cells over the same data period as **Figure 2**. Extracted from the Sieg and Cheshire, 2021 GISRUk abstract on MAUP and Huq data.

Comparing **Figure 3** and **4**, we see that the quadtree object presents higher granularity than aggregating to 250m grid cells. Though **Figure 4** also displays the more concentrated areas, it does not allow for more detail as to where exactly this activity splits within said areas. Choosing a larger grid size coarsens the data, but a smaller size risks the omission of larger amounts of data to prevent disclosure. The quadtree algorithm allows the researcher to have a glimpse of the data without needing to make choices which could alter it. Furthermore, the quadtree object requires less steps than **Figure 4** to make. With pairs of coordinates and the AQuadtree function, a few simple lines of code generate the map, whereas **Figure 4** required spatial joins to an ordnance survey grid and some coordinate system reconversions.

Figure 5: Quadtree of Tower Hamlets using Huq data and a threshold of 10 unique devices by cell. The activity clusters are visible: The A11 is distinguishable by the line of smaller cells traced South-West to North-East. Canary Warf also appears as the hub of activity (red arrow). (8-10am)

Discussion

Quadtree algorithms, such as the one provided by Lagonigro et. al (2020) provide an innovative and automated method for anonymising and representing large sensitive datasets. They allow for spatial aggregation to be moulded around the dataset and helps inform researchers of the range of scales at which their data can be significant. However, they may not be a viable solution for outputting and communicating result, nor for performing geodemographic analysis, as the quadtree products are dynamic and highly changeable with new data inputs. We recommend their use in preliminary and exploratory analysis, as they are an efficient and simple tool to help inform project-specific choices on scale and regionalisation.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the ESRC. We thank Huq industries for providing data, and the UCL Research Ethics Committee for reviewing the project.

References

- Cockings, S., Harfoot, A., Martin, D., & Hornby, D. (2011). Maintaining Existing Zoning Systems Using Automated Zone-Design Techniques: Methods for Creating the 2011 Census Output Geographies for England and Wales: *Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1068/A43601*, 43(10), 2399–2418. <https://doi.org/10.1068/A43601>
- de Montjoye, Y. A., Gambs, S., Blondel, V., Canright, G., de Cordes, N., Deletaille, S., Engø-Monsen, K., Garcia-Herranz, M., Kendall, J., Kerry, C., Krings, G., Letouzé, E., Luengo-Oroz, M., Oliver, N., Rocher, L., Rutherford, A., Smoreda, Z., Steele, J., Wetter, E., ... Bengtsson, L. (2018). On the privacy-conscientious use of mobile phone data. In *Scientific Data* (Vol. 5, Issue 1, pp. 1–6). Nature Publishing Groups. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.286>
- Lagonigro, R., Oller, R., & Carles Martori, J. (2020). *Title Confidentiality of Spatial Point Data*. <https://doi.org/10.2436/20.8080.02.55>
- Lagonigro, R., Oller, R., & Carles Martori, J. (2020). AQuadtree: an R Package for Quadtree Anonymization of Point Data. *R Journal*. <https://web.b.ebscohost.com/abstract?direct=true&profile=ehost&scope=site&authtype=crawler&jrnl=20734859&AN=148792316&h=pa%2FJbkN3O3424TnoH%2BRwTPE9JPK0L2zXCxp%2BAfPtcCtINf1%2BSP5%2B0CqODLG%2Ftx1SVXVz8L5zdAG0yMWthvqWg%3D%3D&crl=c&resultNs=AdminWebAuth&resultLocal=ErrCrlNotAuth&crlhashurl=login.aspx%3Fdirect%3Dtrue%26profile%3Dehost%26scope%3Dsite%26authtype%3Dcrawler%26jrnl%3D20734859%26AN%3D148792316>
- Lovelace, R., Ballas, D., & Watson, M. (2014). A spatial microsimulation approach for the analysis of commuter patterns: from individual to regional levels. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 34, 282–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JTRANGE0.2013.07.008>
- Molloy, J., & Moeckel, R. (2017). Automated design of gradual zone systems. *Open Geospatial Data, Software and Standards 2017 2:1*, 2(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40965-017-0032-5>
- Sieg, L., & Cheshire, J. (2021). *Spatially aggregating mobility data – implications and challenges*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4669903>
- Viegas, J. M., Martínez, L. M., & Silva, E. A. (2009). Effects of the modifiable areal unit problem on the delineation of traffic analysis zones. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 36(4), 625–643. <https://doi.org/10.1068/B34033>

Biographies

Louise Sieg is a PhD Student in Geography at UCL. Her research explores the value and provenance of new forms of data applied to geodemographics.

James Cheshire is Professor of Geographic Information and Cartography at UCL, Director of the UCL Q-Step Centre and Deputy Director of the ESRC Consumer Data Research Centre.